

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

A STUDY ON THE RISK FACTORS IN THE OCCURRENCE OF CEREBRAL INFARCTION AMONG PATIENTS OF STROKE

Dr Munim Kareem, Dr Muhammad Tayyab, Dr Muhammad Talha Liaquat
King Edward Medical University

Article Received: May 2019

Accepted: June 2019

Published: July 2019

Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to determine the frequency of different risk factors in the occurrence of cerebral infarction among patients of stroke.

Methodology: This descriptive research work was carried out in the Mayo Hospital Lahore from December 2017 to November 2018. Total 80 patients suffering from stroke with the cerebral infarction diagnosed by the computed tomography scan of brain and having greater than 20 year of age were the part of this research work. Different risk factors for the occurrence of cerebral infarction were hypertension, habit of cigarette smoking, IHD (Ischemic Heart Diseases), diabetes, dyslipidemias, past history of stroke in the family, TIAs & stenosis of carotid artery analyzed.

Results: We recorded the data of 80 patients suffering from cerebral infarction. Majority of the patients were available with greater than one factor of risk for cerebral infarction. The most common risk factor was hypertension as 53.0%, cigarette smoking in 28.0%, IHD in 32.0%, diabetes mellitus in 24.0%, hyperlipidemia in 28.0%, atrial fibrillation in 23.0%, stenosis of carotid artery in 25.0%, obesity in 13.0% & past history of stroke in the family in 10.0% patients. Physical inactivity was available in 37.0% patients. Male patients outnumbered the female patients (49.0% vs 47.0%). Average age of the males was fifty years and females was fifty-three years.

Conclusions: cerebral infarction is responsible for 78.0% to 83.0% patients of stroke, which is very frequent disorder of neurology. This complication enhances the disability burden as well as the misery for these patients & their families. Majority of the risk factors of CI are modifiable, the prevention and control of these risk factors should be the matter of concern of populations.

Key Words: CI, cerebral, population, occurrence, methodology, stroke, misery, inactivity, diabetes, hypertension, cigarette.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Munim Kareem,
King Edward Medical University.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Munim Kareem et al., *A Study On The Risk Factors In The Occurrence Of Cerebral Infarction Among Patients Of Stroke.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[07].

INTRODUCTION:

The neurological deficiency occurring for greater than 24 hours is stroke. cerebral infarction is responsible for 78.0% to 83.0% stroke patients [1]. Stroke is the cause of death of approximately 5 million peoples every year making this disease 2nd important reason of death in the whole world. About 15 million people are available with non-fatal stroke every year and about 1/3rd become permanently disable as a result [2]. There are some non-modifiable factors of risk for cerebral infarction as age, gender, past history of the family, ethnicity & race. Some modifiable factors of risk for CI are diabetes, hypertension, heart diseases, hyperlipidemia, habit of cigarette smoking, the consumption of alcohol & inactivity [3]. The aim of this research work is to determine the risk factors for cerebral infarction & to evaluate that there are many modifiable factors whose prevention is possible with the proper awareness of the population and therapy of the present risk factors.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work was carried out in the Mayo Hospital Lahore from December 2017 to November 2018. Ninety percent patients of stroke got admission from the ward of emergency and remaining patients were from outpatient department. Patients with the following criteria were the part of this research work:

1. All the patients were suffering from stroke for the very first time appeared within twenty-four hours after the start of the symptoms.
2. All the patients were having twenty years of age or more from both genders.
3. Computed tomography confirmed the incidence of cerebral infarction.

The patients of stroke with reason other than cerebral infarction & unstable patients requiring intensive care were not the part of this research work. We gathered the elaborate information of the patients particularly about the factors of risks for cerebral infarction as diabetes, IHD, hypertension, habit of cigarette smoking, physical inactivity, and consumption of alcohol and the utilization of contraception pills for female patients. After the complete examination, patients underwent investigation like percentage of Hb, blood glucose level, chest X-ray, lipid profile of serum, electrocardiograph, and computed tomography scan of the brain. For some patients, we carried out the Doppler study & performed echocardiography.

The diagnosis of the cerebral infarction carried out when computed tomography scan of the brain displayed hypo-dense region corresponding to the medical view. The criteria of every risk factor for the patients having stroke because of cerebral infarction was according to the standard of WHO. These important risk factors were IHD, smoking, Diabetes mellitus, obesity, past history of the family, hypertension or high blood pressure.

RESULTS:

We recorded the data of 80 patients of cerebral infarction in this research work. In this research work, there was slightly dominancy of the male patients (49.0% vs 47.0%) with the range of age from twenty-one to seventy-eight years. With an average age of fifty years, whereas females were older with having the range of age from twenty four to eighty three years with an average age of fifty three years. The most prone age for the occurrence was 7th decade of life. Majority of the patients were available with greater than one risk factors as mentioned in Table-1.

Table-I: Frequency of Risk Factors of Cerebral Infarction in Stroke Patients

No. of risk factors	Patients
1	17.0
2	21.0
3	35.0
4	13.0
5	4.0

Most frequent risk factor among patients was hypertension available in 53.0% patients. Out of these 53.0%, 43.0% patients were present as known hypertensive & 8.0% patients were not aware about this complication. We found a positive background of cigarette smoking in 28.0% patients. Diabetes was available in 24.0% patient. Total 13 patients were

utilizing drugs for glycemic control but remaining were not paying attention. Atrial fibrillation was present in 23.0% patients, hyperlipidemia in 28.0% patients & IHD in 32.0% patients as describes in Table-2. Majority of the patients were from the lower middle social class. The men stay at the hospital was ten days. The rate of mortality was 6.0%.

Table-II: Frequency of Risk Factors of Cerebral Infarction in Stroke Patients (N = 80)

Risk Factors	No. of Patients
Hypertension (HTN)	53.0
Smoking	28.0
Ischemic heart disease	32.0
Hyperlipidemia	28.0
Diabetes (DM)	24.0
Carotid artery stenosis	25.0
Atrial fibrillation	23.0
Corpulence	13.0
Stroke patients in family members	10.0
Comfort / Inactivity	37.0

DISCUSSION:

The danger of stroke rises with age [4] & average age in this research work was 49.25 years which was very low than the seventy years as stated by Sacco RL [5] and slightly less than fifty-three years as stated by Akhter [6]. In both genders, most vulnerable age for the Cerebral infarction was sixty to seventy years as stated by Al-Rajeh [7], the most important risk factor for Cerebral infarction in this research work was hypertension in this research work, available in 53.0% patient. This is similar rate as stated by Ali-L [8] & Al-Rajeh [7] and less than the 60.0% as stated by Nasir Mehmood [9] & 61.0% as stated by Rafiq [6] & much less than as stated by Burgin WS (65.0%) [10] & FeiginVL (85.0%) [11]. Hypertension is well-established factor of risk for Cerebral infarction [12]. The reduction of the danger of stroke is possible at least 38.0% with the control of hypertension [13]. CI is much common in the patients suffering from diabetes mellitus [14]. Qureshi reported 11.60% of CI in the patients of diabetes [15]. Other research works showed the range of 13.0% to 36.0% patients of CI in diabetics [16].

Smoking has association with the high risk of Cerebral infarction and this risk increases with the quantity of cigarettes per day [17]. We find this factor in 28.0% patients, which is much higher than some research works [9, 18] and much less than the research works as stated by Greenland (81.0%) [19].

We discovered dyslipidemia in 28.0% patients which is more than other research works [8, 9]. Obesity was present in 13.0% patients as a risk factor for Cerebral infarction. Ansari discovered same rate in his research work [20]. We found the atrial fibrillation in 23.0% patients which was very high as stated by Basharat (7.0%) [21] & Burgin-WS (11.0%) [10]. Silent Cerebral infarction and angina pectoris enhances the danger of the ischemic stroke [22]. IHD was present in 32.0% patients of this research work which is close as

stated by Al-Rajeh (33.0%) [7]. Stenosis of high grade of the extra-cranial carotid artery is available in 1/4th of the ischemic strokes and it has more association to the cortical infarction [23]. In this research work, stenosis of carotid artery was present in 25.0% patients. This is much similar as stated by Chang YJ (24.30%) [24] & much high as discovered by Basharat (8.0%) [21]. Some current research works display that physical inactivity can increase the danger of Cerebral infarction [25]. Past history of the stroke in the family was present in 10.0% patients of this research work which is a little bit greater than stated by other research works [26]. The use of contraceptives, consumption of alcohol & sleep apnea are also the risk factors for CI [27-30] but our research did not discovered these risk factors. Stroke is main reason behind high rate of morbidity as well as mortality. In current research work, rate of mortality was 6.0%. This rate is much less than 25.0% as stated by Sheikh AA [31] & 34.0% as discovered by Marzban M [32].

CONCLUSION:

CI is responsible for 78.0% to 83.0% patients of stroke which is very disorder of neurology. Most important risk factors of Cerebral infarction are hypertension, habit of cigarette smoking, IHD, hyperlipidemia and physical inactivity, majority of the risk factors are modifiable with the suitable education and awareness of patients.

REFERENCES:

1. Sacco RL, Gan R, Boden-Albala B, Lin IF, Kargman DE, Hauser WA, et al. Leisure time physical activity and ischemic stroke risk: The North Manhattan stroke study. *Stroke* 1998; 29:380-7.
2. Akhter W. Stroke: The common modifiable risk factors and inpatient outcome. Dissertation College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP). Med/3510-A / 2001.
3. Al-Rajeh S, Adnan A, Gulnar N, Emmanuel I. Stroke in a Saudi Arabian National Guard

- Community: Analysis of 500 consecutive cases from a population-based hospital. *Stroke* 1993; 24:16 35-9.
4. Ali L, Jamil H, Shah MA. Risk factors in Stroke. *J Coll Phys Surg Pak* 1997;7(1):7-10.
 5. Nasir M. Clinical Presentation of cerebral infarction and its association with major risk factors. Dissertation College of physicians and surgeons Pakistan (CPSP). Med/959/2000.
 6. Burgin WS, Staub L, Chan W, Wein TH, Felberg RA, Grotta JC, et al. Acute stroke care in nonurban emergency departments. *Neurology* 2001;11,57(11):2006-12.
 7. Feigin VL, Weibers DO, Nikitin YP, O'Fallen WMI, Whisnant JP. Risk factors for ischemic strokes in a Russian Community: A population-based case control study. *Stroke* 1998; 29:34-9.
 8. Warlow CP, Dennis MS, Van Gijn J, Hankely GL, Sandercock PAG, Bamford J, et al. *Stroke: A practical guideline to management*, 2nd ed. Blackwell scientific publications; Oxford, 2000.
 9. Kissela B, Schneider A, Kleindorfer D, Khoury J, Miller R, Alwell K, et al. Stroke in biracial population: the excess burden of stroke among blacks. *Stroke* 2004; 35:426-31.
 10. Hoshida S, Kario K, Mitsuhashi T, Sato Y, Umeda Y, Katsuki T, et al. Different patterns of silent cerebral infarct in patients with coronary artery disease or hypertension. *Am J Hypertens* 2001;14(6 Pt 1):509-15.
 11. Fayyaz M. Risk factors and early prognosis in stroke. *Annals* 1999;5(1):12-15.
 12. Banerjee TK, Mukerjee CS, Sarkhel A. Stroke in urban population of Calcutta-an epidemiological study. *Neuro epidemiology* 2001;20(3):201-7.
 13. Sheikh AA. Cerebrovascular accidents in hypertensive subjects. Dissertation College of physicians and surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) Med/970-2000.
 14. Qureshi LI, Safdar K, Patel M, Janssen RS, Frankel MR. Stroke in young black patients. Risk factors, subtypes and prognosis. *Stroke*. 1995, 26:1995-8.
 15. Schneider AT, Pancioli AM, Khoury JC, Rademacher E, Tuchfarber A, Miller R, et al. Trends in Community Knowledge of the warning signs and risk factors of stroke. *JAMA* 2003; 289:343-6.
 16. Sanderg O, Franklin KA, Bucht G, Gustafson Y, Sleep apnea, delirium, depressed mood, cognition and ADL ability after stroke. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 2001;49(4):391-7.
 17. Daven PR, Denis M. Neurological emergencies: Acute Stroke. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 2000; 68:277-88.
 18. Rodriguez BL, D'Agostino R, Abbott RD, Kagan A, Burchfiel CM, Yano K, et al. Risk of hospitalized stroke in men enrolled in the Honolulu heart program and Framingham study: A comparison of incidence and risk factor effects. *Stroke* 2002; 33:230-6.
 19. Pancioli AM, Broderick J, Kothari R, Brott T, Tuchfarber A, Miller R, et al. Public perception of stroke warning signs and knowledge of potential risk factors. *JAMA* 1998; 279:1288-92.
 20. Javed MA, Ahmed M, Sial MSH, Naheed T. Risk factor in stroke. *Pak. J Neurol* 1998; 4:55-8.
 21. Kjaergaard JJ, Gelvan A. Risk factors for ischemic stroke in young Greenlanders: *Int J Circumpolar Health* 2004;63,2:287-9.
 22. Ansari AK. Stroke in young adults: Identification of risk factors and prognosis. *Pak J Med Sci* 1999; 38:10-13.
 23. Marzban M. Risk factors for stroke patients in Civil Hospital Quetta. Dissertation College of physicians and surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) Med/690/1998.
 24. Basharat AR, Yousaf M. Frequency of known risk factors for stroke in poor patients admitted to Lahore General Hospital in 2000. *Pak J Med Sci* 2002;18(4):280-3.
 25. Aronow WS, Ahn C, Gutstein H. Incidence of new athero-thrombotic brain infarction in older persons with prior myocardial infarction and serum low density lipoprotein cholesterol $\geq$ 125mg/dl treated with statins versus no lipid-lowering drug. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci* 2002;57(5):333-5.
 26. Abu-Rahma, AF, Wuluj T Jr, Crotty, B. Carotid plaque ultrasonic heterogeneity and severity of stenosis stroke. 2002; 33:1772-5.
 27. Chang YJ, Ryu SJ, Lin SK. Carotid artery stenosis is ischemic stroke patients with non-valvular atrial fibrillation. *Cerebrovasc Dis* 2002;13(1):16-20.
 28. Hu FB, Stampfer MJ, Colditz GA, Ascherio A, Rexrode KM, Willett WC, et al. Physical activity and risk of stroke in women. *JAMA* 2000; 283:2961-7.
 29. Wolfe CDA, Rudd AG, Howard R. Incidence and case fatality rates of stroke subtypes in a multiethnic population: the south London stroke register. *J Neurology Psychi* 2002; 72:211-6.
 30. Milhau D, Bogousslavsky J, Van Melle G, Liot P. Ischemic stroke and active migraine. *Neurology* 2001;27,57(10):1805-11.
 31. Bushnell CD, Samsa GP and Goldstein LB. Hormone replacement therapy and ischemic stroke severity in women: A case control study. *Neurology* 2001;22,56(10):1304-7.
 32. Haepniemi H, Hillborn M, Juvela S. Life style associated risk factors for acute brain infarction

among persons of working age. Stroke
1997;8(1):26-30.